

Open circuit voltage recovery in GaAsSbN-based solar cells due to elimination of deep N-related radiative states

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ABSTRACT

In this work we investigate the effect of rapid thermal annealing (RTA) on the performance of solar cells consisting of different GaAsSbN-based structures and correlate the device results with modifications of the optical and structural properties of the alloy. In particular, bulk layers grown at different growth rates and type-II GaAsSb/GaAsN superlattices with different period thickness are analyzed. We find evidences of material quality improvement after the annealing process such as a reduction of N-related radiative defects and Sb clusters. These RTA-induced changes lead to a notable enhancement of the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}), which results in values of the bandgap-voltage offset ($W_{oc} = E_g/q - V_{oc}$) comparable to that of a reference GaAs solar cell. The decrease in W_{oc} after annealing correlates with the reduced radiative recombination at low energy N-related sub-bandgap states. These results identify radiative recombination in a broad band of deep defect states as a main source of V_{oc} degradation in GaAsSbN solar cells.

KEYWORDS: *Molecular Beam epitaxy, GaAsSbN, multi-junction solar cells, superlattices, rapid thermal annealing, open circuit voltage.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Dilute-nitride semiconductor alloys are well known as suitable materials for photonic applications [1,2]. Amongst them, the GaAsSbN alloy has some potential advantages: The presence of Sb increases the efficiency of N incorporation in the compound, diminishes N migration and the formation of nitrogen-related defects, and favors two-dimensional growth because of the Sb surfactant effect [3,4,5]. Moreover, GaAsSbN allows a straightforward control of the band structure; this is explained by a double-band anticrossing (DBAC) model, according to which Sb controls the valence band edge position, while N controls the conduction band edge [6]. GaAsSbN also provides good lattice parameter control: according to Vegard's law, Sb fully counteracts the tensile strain caused by N in GaAs for an [Sb] to [N] ratio of around 2.8 ($[Sb]/[N] \approx 2.8$) [7]. The bandgap of this

alloy can be therefore readily tuned to the 1.0-1.15 eV region while keeping lattice-matching to GaAs, which makes it very interesting for solar cell applications.

Indeed, this ability makes GaAsSbN a suitable candidate for the implementation of optimum GaAs/Ge-based multi-junction solar cell (MJSCs) designs without the need of complex technologies such as inverted metamorphic structures or wafer bonding. Detailed balance limit calculations predict that a promising cell architecture hypothetically surpassing the efficiency of commercially available (Al)GaInP (1.9 eV)/(In)GaAs (1.4 eV)/Ge (0.7 eV) triple junction solar cells would consist of replacing the Ge layer with a 1.0–1.15 eV sub-cell or alternatively including the 1.0–1.15 eV sub-cell within a quadruple junction solar cell [8,9]. This architecture has been predicted to increase the power conversion efficiency over 53% under sunlight concentration [10,11,12]. Whence, following such expectations, bulk layers of GaAsSbN material have already been experimentally implemented as 1 eV bandgap layers for MJSC applications [13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20]. However, as far as we know, the efficiencies achieved until now have not approached the predicted values, mainly due to difficulties in achieving high-quality material [21]. In order to avoid such problems, different strategies are currently under investigation, such as the optimization of V-V [4] or III-V [22] flux ratios, growth temperature [23], growth rates [24], and other growth-related parameters [14,25]. Replacing GaAsSbN bulk layers with GaAsSb/GaAsN superlattices (SLs) has also been recently suggested as an alternative and promising way to increase the solar cell efficiency [26,27]. These structures could offer several advantages over the bulk material, such as a better compositional control, a higher crystalline quality and longer minority carrier lifetimes [26,27,28]. It must be noticed that the poor performance of GaAsSbN in photovoltaics is typically attributed to non-radiative recombination rates, disregarding the possible effect of sub-bandgap radiative states.

Besides these growth-based strategies, a post-growth rapid thermal annealing (RTA) treatment could further improve the structural, optical and electrical properties of GaAsSbN alloys. In fact, annealing has been shown to reduce the density of N-related point defects and to improve the alloy homogeneity, as well as to improve the optical properties in dilute nitrides [29,30,31] and, particularly, in GaAsSbN [32,33,34]. RTA process has also been applied to dilute nitrides conceived for photovoltaic uses [17,18,35,36,37], but the actual impact of RTA on solar cell performance has been barely analyzed in depth. The observed improvements are typically attributed to reduced non-radiative recombination rates, but, again, the possible influence on N-related radiative states has not been investigated to date. In this work, we first study the effect of RTA on the optical and

structural properties of different GaAsSbN-based structures, namely: bulk layers grown at different growth rates and SLs with different period thickness. Then we analyze the performance of the as-grown and annealed solar cells and correlate the device results with modifications on material properties and, particularly, the role of optically active gap states.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

All the samples were grown in a solid source molecular beam epitaxy Riber 32 system. The substrate consists of (001) GaAs n+ wafer on which a 250 nm-thick GaAs buffer layer was deposited. It is over this buffer where the active GaAs(Sb)(N) structure was grown. The active layer was capped with a 50 nm GaAs layer. To achieve p-i-n structures, in some of the samples the buffer layer was Si-doped, and the capping layer Be-doped. In such cases the nominal n and p-type doping concentrations were $2 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The active layer was grown at a temperature of 470° C. The atomic N flux is provided by a radio frequency plasma source using a 0.1 sccm flow of N₂ and monitored through the optical emission detection (OED) of the atomic N, which is proportional to the N flux. A hermetic valve placed behind the plasma source provides accurate control over N flux, avoiding the presence of N background in the structure and confining it on the corresponding nominal layers [38]. As₄, Ga, Sb₄, Si and Be fluxes are provided by effusion cells. Samples are grown under As₄ overpressure conditions with an As beam equivalent pressure of 1.8^{-5} Torr. Reflective high-energy electron diffraction (RHEED) assesses the two-dimensional growth mode and allows controlling the growth rate. RTA cycles at different temperatures were performed in an Ulvac MILA-3000 rapid thermal annealer during 30 seconds under a N₂ inert atmosphere.

High-resolution X-ray diffraction (HR-XRD) rocking-curve scans using the Cu-Kα₁ line (1.54056 Å) were performed with an X'Pert Pro Pan'alytical commercial system.

High- and low-angle annular dark-field (HA/LA)ADF imaging and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy mapping were simultaneously acquired in STEM mode with a double aberration corrected FEI Titan3 Cubed Themis operated at 200 kV. The EDX mapping and profiling was carried out with four embedded Bruker SDD detectors using ChemiSTEM technology and processed using Bruker's ESPRIT software.

Low temperature (15 K) photoluminescence (PL) measurements were carried out using a He-Ne laser with a power of 3 mW. The emitted light was dispersed through a 1-m spectrometer and detected using a liquid-nitrogen cooled Ge-detector and amplified with standard lock-in techniques.

The p-i-n solar cells were subsequently fabricated as 200 μm -diameter mesa-etched devices using standard processing techniques. The mesa structure of the devices was created through wet etching using a $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ (1:1:8) solution. The p-type Au/Au-Zn/Au (100/800/2000 Å) contact was evaporated on top of the mesas and the n-type Au-Ge/Au (800/2000 Å) contact was evaporated on the back side of the substrate. Both contacts were subsequently annealed at 380 °C during 30 seconds under N_2H_2 atmosphere. It must be noticed that the solar cell structure is not optimized. Neither the thickness nor the doping level of the absorber and emitter regions were optimized, and no window layer or anti-reflection coating were deposited, as the purpose of our study is at this stage mainly comparative.

Photocurrent (PC) spectra were measured using a K2401 Keithley sourcemeter, a K6514 Keithley System electrometer, a QTH lamp and a 0.34-m monochromator. The external quantum efficiency (EQE) was calculated from the PC data considering the QTH lamp power density and the diode top metal-free area.

Finally, AM1.5G current-voltage curves were measured using an Oriel solar simulator with sample temperature control at 25° C.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. N-related deep radiative defects

In order to investigate the presence of optically active defects in GaAsSbN alloys that could affect the performance of solar cells, we compare the PL of a first series of samples: two ternary bulk samples, the first one containing only Sb (named *GaAsSb*) and the second one containing only N (named *GaAsN*) and one bulk quaternary sample containing both Sb and N (named *GaAsSbN*). PL spectrum from a GaAs substrate is also included for reference. These three samples have the same active region thickness (200 nm) and were grown under the same Sb and N fluxes, which corresponds with nominal contents of 2.2% Sb and 1.1% N. 15 K PL measurements of this set of samples are shown in Fig. 1(a). *GaAsN* and *GaAsSbN* samples show a dominant emission peak corresponding with the band edge luminescence at 1.24 and 1.20 eV, respectively, and a weaker broad band emission at lower energies, from about 0.75 eV to around 1.05 eV, more intense in the ternary *GaAsN* than in *GaAsSbN* sample. Such weaker sub-bandgap PL band is not present in *GaAsSb* or GaAs substrate spectra. The evolution of the low energy band with the N content was investigated through a second series of three samples consisting on 200 nm-thick GaAsN layers with 0.4%, 0.6% and 0.9% of N respectively, along with the previous *GaAsN* sample with 1.1% N. As shown in Fig.

1(b), the sub-bandgap emission intensity increases with the N content in the structure. Remarkably, the peak energy of this band is not shifted with the N content, while its integrated intensity increases becoming even similar to that of the band edge emission for N contents around 1%. At the other end, the striking reduction of the sub-bandgap emission observed in Fig. 1(a) with the addition of Sb was also analyzed in a third set of samples. In this third series of samples, the N content is fixed to 1.8%, while the Sb flux increases leading to Sb contents from around 3% to 10%. As shown in Fig. 1(c), the low energy band emission intensity progressively decreases with the increasing Sb content in the alloy. Ultimately, for the highest Sb content, the broad band emission virtually disappears (the peak appearing at 0.96 eV corresponds to the band edge emission of the sample).

There is, therefore, a significant density of states within the bandgap at 450 meV below the conduction band in N-containing samples. The highest energy states of this deep band overlap with band tail states typically observed in diluted nitrides, since the PL signal does not go to zero between the two peaks. This emission band can be attributed to the existence of N-induced radiative defects and not to the presence of Sb-related defects, being its intensity directly related to the N concentration. On the contrary, Sb helps reduce the N-induced defect density, as the inclusion of Sb to form the quaternary *GaAsSbN* reduces the emission intensity related to such N-induced defects. Indeed, Sb contents of ~10% are enough to virtually suppress the PL emission for an N content close to 2%. Similar low-energy emission bands have been reported previously on GaAsN layers [39,40,41] and on GaAsSbN [25,32,42,43], being ascribed to the presence of deep defects associated to N or Sb, or to residual impurities. However, the actual origin of this emission band remained unidentified.

3.2. Effect of RTA on luminescence

RTA cycles were performed in p-i-n structures with a 750 nm-thick GaAsSbN intrinsic region in order to subsequently study its impact on solar cell performance. Different layers were grown: two bulk samples grown at different growth rates, 1ML/s (the standard growth rate of GaAs-related compounds) and 2ML/s, (samples *Bulk 1ML/s* and *Bulk 2ML/s*, respectively) and two type-II GaAsSb/GaAsN SLs with 12 and 6 nm period thickness grown at 1 ML/s (*SL-II 12* and *SL-II 6*, respectively). In all cases N and Sb fluxes were chosen to obtain samples with a bandgap around 1.15 eV; N and Sb fluxes in the 2 ML/s sample were adjusted to provide the same N and Sb incorporation than in the 1 ML/s samples. Three different temperatures, 750, 800 and 850° C, were employed to anneal different pieces of each structure. Preliminary PL measurements were used to test the RTA temperature case by case. The optimum temperature is defined as that leading to

maximum band edge PL peak intensity, minimum full width at half maximum (FWHM) and maximum PL peak integrated intensity. Following these evaluation criteria, the RTA temperature chosen for device processing was 800 °C for all samples.

15 K PL spectra taken over the same sample pieces before and after RTA at 800° C (as-grown and RTA, respectively) are represented in Fig. 2. PL spectra in all samples present the main peak corresponding to the bandgap energy (GAP peak) and the sub-bandgap broad band attributed to N-related states previously observed (N peak). Integrated intensity values of both peaks (I_{GAP} and I_{N} , respectively) and full width at half maximum of main peak (FWHM_{GAP}) of each as-grown and RTA sample are presented in Table 1, as well as the blue-shift of the main peak after RTA ($\text{Blue-shift}_{\text{GAP}}$).

Regarding the as-grown samples, the *Bulk 1ML/s* sample has a slightly more intense GAP peak than the *Bulk 2ML/s* sample, but both have similar N peak emission in terms of shape and integrated intensity. On the other hand, the *SL-II 12* has by far the most intense GAP peak, which could be a result of a better crystal quality and/or quantum confinement [26], and the *SL-II 6* sample has the less intense GAP peak but the strongest N peak in terms of integrated intensity. Focusing on the N-related emission band, its integrated intensity is similar in both bulk samples, and larger in *SL-II 12* and *SL-II 6* samples. This agrees with the Sb-induced reduction of the N-related sub-bandgap emission mentioned earlier: since N and Sb are spatially separated in the SLs, a stronger emission would be expected from the pure GaAsN layers than from GaAsSbN.

A blue-shift of the main peak is observed after RTA in all spectra. PL blue-shift induced by annealing is a commonly observed effect in dilute nitrides such as GaInNAs and GaInNASb and has been attributed to Ga/In intermixing, N-atom out diffusion of the alloy or N-bonding reorganization [30,36,44,45]. Blue-shifts with values very similar to those obtained here have also been observed in GaAsSbN bulk and quantum well (QW) structures, and attributed to atomic As/Sb interdiffusion [43], material reorganization [18,34], or a reduction of the density of tail-states associated with native defects present in dilute nitrides [32]. Remarkably, the blue-shift in all cited works is always accompanied by an increase of the band to band PL intensity and a decrease of the FWHM.

In our case, the reduction of the FWHM of the main peak after RTA in all samples points out to the removal of clusters and composition modulation, improving the homogeneity of the N and Sb distribution. However, though the main PL peak intensity increases after RTA in SL samples (especially in *SL-II 12* sample), this does not happen in bulk samples. The reduction of the band edge emission intensity in bulk structures after RTA is an unexpected result. Moreover, the reduction of

both peaks (GAP and N peaks, respectively) after RTA is very similar, as if it were originated by increased non-radiative recombination, contrary to what would be expected [30,31,46]. A reduced carrier localization due to potential fluctuations after RTA could also have something to do with the observed behavior in bulk samples, while recombination from localized states would be strongly reduced in the SLs due to the spatial separation of electrons and holes in the N- and Sb-induced potential wells, respectively. Remarkably, despite the different behavior of the band edge peak after annealing in the bulk and SLs, the RTA process induces a similar reduction of the sub-bandgap emission band on every sample. The strong reduction of integrated intensity of the N peak after RTA points to a significant reduction of the density of deep sub-bandgap states and, therefore, to the annihilation of N-related radiative defects.

3.3. Structural characterization

HR-XRD measurements were performed on the same pieces as PL measurements, before and after the RTA process. Fig. 3 shows two representative cases, spectra corresponding to *Bulk 1ML/s* and *SL-II 12* samples. The central peak at 33.0239° corresponds to GaAs. The position of the active layer diffraction peak (which in the *SL-II 12* spectra coincides with the substrate peak because of exact lattice matching) does not undergo any variation after the RTA process. That means that the average N-Sb composition in the lattice structure remains unaltered. Furthermore, the diffraction peak of the active layer becomes sharper after the annealing process, pointing out to an improvement in crystal quality through the thermal treatment. Focusing on *SL-II 12* spectra, the secondary diffraction peaks that characterize the SL periodicity, are preserved after annealing, so that the SL periodicity and the flatness of the well-barrier interfaces have not been deteriorated during the annealing process. Therefore, no Sb-N intermixing between adjacent layers, that would ultimately transform the SL in a bulk structure, takes place during RTA.

Structural characterization is completed with TEM analysis. In the case of diluted nitride GaAs-based alloys, the strong difference between As and N atomic radius produces a large distortion in the structure that has a strong impact on the ADF scattering intensity, predominating over Z-contrast scattering in LAADF conditions [47,48]. Figure 4 (a) shows LAADF images of both as-grown and RTA *SL-II 12* samples. The N-containing layers are easily identified since they present a much brighter contrast than the GaAsSb layers [27,49]. Abrupt interfaces with symmetrical and squared N profiles along the growth direction can be seen in both samples, which indicates a very low segregation of N outside the GaAsN layers even after the RTA. Fig. 4(b) shows EDX maps of the Sb elemental

distribution taken over the same regions. N maps cannot be obtained by this technique although studies to reveal the quantitative N distribution are currently ongoing. The Sb maps reveal the existence of a higher density of clusters with a Sb composition up to 7.0% in the GaAsSb layers in the as-grown sample. Instead, RTA sample maps point towards a more homogenous Sb distribution with a reduction of the Sb cluster density, as well as more abrupt interfaces [49].

The corresponding Sb content profiles along the growth and in-plane directions are plotted in Fig. 4(c). Remarkably, the Sb profiles along the growth direction barely exhibit any difference between as-grown and annealed samples. These measurements demonstrate that neither Sb nor N are segregated along the growth direction after RTA, maintaining the original profiles. On the other hand, Sb profiles along in-plane direction in one of the GaAsSb layers in the as-grown sample show a high oscillation of the Sb content between 2.5% and 6.5%, which is reduced after RTA, oscillating only from 3.5% to 5.5%. The mean Sb contents and the corresponding standard deviations extracted from these data are 4.5% and 0.7% for the as-grown and 4.6% and 0.4% for the RTA samples, respectively, which confirms the significant homogenization of the Sb composition obtained during annealing.

3.4. Solar cell performance

I-V curves taken under AM1.5G conditions of as-grown and annealed p-i-n diodes were measured to investigate the impact of RTA on solar cell performance. The results are shown in Fig. 5. Short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), conversion efficiency and fill factor (FF) are shown in Table 2. It must be noticed here that the poor performance is partially due to the un-optimized solar cell structures, as explained in the experimental section. The performance of the as-grown bulk solar cell grown at a faster rate is better than that of the standard growth rate counterpart, which indicates that using high growth rates in the range of 2 ML/s could be an adequate strategy to improve the performance of GaAsSbN solar cells. The short circuit current density (J_{sc}) of *SL-II 12* is much lower than that of the rest of the samples and leads to a much lower conversion efficiency. This is due to transport problems caused by carrier localization in the QWs [26], which makes this structure inadequate as a solar cell. Nevertheless, the J_{sc} of *SL-II 6* is comparable to those of the bulk samples, as a result of better carrier extraction in samples with reduced SL period because of the formation of minibands [50]. However, J_{sc} is always reduced after RTA. The origin of this reduction is under investigation but it could be related to the elimination of

the optically active deep states and the observed blue-shift in the band edge, which effectively results in a larger “bandgap” material and, therefore, a lower J_{SC} .

The FF values are similar before and after RTA for both bulk samples. However, the FF significantly increases in SL samples: 22% relative in *SL-II 12* and 10% in *SL-II 6*. The highest value of the FF (67%) is obtained for the *SL-II 6* annealed device.

The V_{OC} of all structures noticeably increases after RTA. The relative increment is similar in all structures: 31%, 27%, 35% and 31% for *bulk 1ML/s*, *bulk 2ML/s*, *SL-II 12* and *SL-II 6*, respectively. A similar V_{OC} increase (around 31%) was obtained after optimum annealing process in bulk GaInNASb solar cells [36], being attributed to the elimination of non-radiative recombination centers.

The inset of Fig. 5 shows the difference in integrated intensity of the low energy broad PL band between as-grown and RTA samples (ΔI_N) and the corresponding bandgap-voltage offset (ΔW_{OC} , with $W_{OC}=E_G/q-V_{OC}$). The (effective) bandgap energy value of each sample is estimated from EQE spectra (not shown). We use the W_{OC} parameter because V_{OC} is not a fair indicator to compare materials of different bandgaps [51]. ΔW_{OC} therefore accounts also for the blue-shift observed after RTA. A correlation seems to exist between ΔI_N and ΔW_{OC} for each type of cell. This fact indicates that the increase of the V_{OC} after RTA is related to the reduction of the density of N-related deep radiative defects. There is no correlation with the evolution of the intensity of the band edge PL peak, which would typically be affected by non-radiative recombination. Indeed, I_{GAP} decreases in the bulk samples. Although the reduction of non-radiative defects could also contribute to the increase of the V_{OC} , our results indicate that it is not the main factor. Instead, the reduction of N-related radiative defects upon annealing results in reduced radiative recombination of carriers photogenerated above the bandgap, as evidenced in the PL by the reduced I_N after RTA. Moreover, the reduction of the density of deep radiative levels would rise the electron quasi-Fermi level for a given density of photogenerated carriers, resulting in a larger V_{OC} . Besides this, the composition homogenization observed after RTA could also contribute to enhance the V_{OC} by reducing carrier trapping (and eventually radiative recombination) at the potential wells.

The W_{OC} values for all the samples before and after annealing are represented in Fig. 6 as a function of their respective bandgap energy, together with that of a reference GaAs solar cell (the high values obtained for the GaAs cell are due to the un-optimized solar cell structure, as described previously. In the ideal case, W_{OC} is independent from the bandgap of the cell. A low W_{OC} value is indicative of a

good solar cell material quality. Therefore, W_{oc} values close to the dotted line indicate a material quality similar to that of GaAs. The W_{oc} values of the as-grown GaAsSbN-based solar cells are all above the reference line. This is typically the case of diluted nitrides, which deviate from the approximately constant W_{oc} obtained for many other materials; indeed, W_{oc} values ~ 200 mV larger than those of GaAs are obtained for GaInNAs with a 1.05 eV bandgap [51]. Nevertheless, the W_{oc} parameter is significantly reduced when the structure is annealed because of the beneficial effects of the thermal treatment shown previously. The two bulk samples and the *SL-II 6* have slightly lower W_{oc} values than our reference GaAs when annealed, indicating comparable material quality to GaAs. The RTA process allows bringing the W_{oc} of GaAsSbN to the level of the rest of high-quality materials. This is a very promising result highlighting that integration of such structures as efficient sub-cells in lattice-matched GaAs/Ge-based MJSCs should be possible after the appropriate annealing process.

4. CONCLUSION

The application of a carefully chosen RTA process at 800 °C to GaAsSbN layers has been shown to improve the crystalline quality of the alloy. In particular, RTA results in a more homogeneous Sb distribution and a reduced density of N-related radiative defects. This holds not only for the quaternary material grown under standard growth conditions, but also for alternative growth approaches, such as high-rate grown GaAsSbN or type-II GaAsSb/GaAsN SL structures. The application of such an RTA process to GaAsSbN-based solar cells improves significantly the V_{oc} in all the GaAsSbN-based solar cells. This seems to be related to the reduced density of deep radiative centers more than to reduced non-radiative recombination. Remarkably, the bandgap-voltage offset of the annealed GaAsSbN solar cells is equivalent or even lower than that of a reference GaAs cell, which indicates high material quality and represents an important step towards its integration in GaAs/Ge-based MJSCs.

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Figure 1: Photoluminescence spectra taken at low temperature (15 K) of different series of samples. Features observed in the 0.9 eV region in every spectrum are related with water absorption in the air. (a) Spectra of *GaAsSb*, *GaAsN*, *GaAsSbN* samples grown using the same Sb and N fluxes and spectrum of a *GaAs* substrate as a reference. (b) Spectra of ternary *GaAsN* samples with different N contents. (c) Spectra of quaternary *GaAsSbN* samples with fixed N content and increasing Sb contents.

Figure 2: Photoluminescence spectra taken at low temperature (15 K) of samples *Bulk 1ML/s*, *Bulk 2ML/s*, *SL-II 12* and *SL-II 6* as-grown (blue lines) and after RTA at 800° C (red lines).

Figure 3. HR-XRD spectra of *Bulk 1ML/s* and *SL-II 12* samples as-grown (solid lines) and after RTA (dotted lines).

Figure 4: (a) LAADF images of *SL-II 12* sample as-grown and after RTA. The brighter layers correspond to the GaAsN layers. (b) Sb EDX maps of *SL-II 12* sample as-grown and after RTA. (c) Sb content profiles of *SL-II 12* sample as-grown and after RTA obtained from the EDX maps along two different directions: growth direction and in-plane direction.

Figure 5: AM1.5G I-V curves of *Bulk 1ML/s*, *Bulk 2ML/s*, *SL-II 12* and *SL-II 6* solar cells as-grown (left) and after RTA (right). The inset of the figure on the right shows the difference in integrated intensity of the low energy broad PL band between RTA and as-grown samples (ΔI_N) on the left axis, and the difference in bandgap-voltage offset ($W_{oc}=E_g/q-V_{oc}$) also between RTA and as-grown samples (ΔW_{oc}) on the right axis.

Figure 6: Bandgap-voltage offset ($W_{oc}=E_g/q-V_{oc}$) of samples *Bulk 1ML/s*, *Bulk 2ML/s*, *SL-II 12* and *SL-II 6*, as-grown (black) and after RTA (red) as a function of their band gap energy. The value of a *GaAs* reference sample is also shown. Dotted line represents W_{oc} values indicating a material quality similar to that of *GaAs*.

Sample	I_{GAP} (a. u.)		$FWHM_{GAP}$ (meV)		Blue-shift $_{GAP}$ (meV)	I_N (a. u.)	
	as-grown	RTA	as-grown	RTA		as-grown	RTA
<i>Bulk 1ML/s</i>	0.574	0.157	69	36	45	0.512	0.136
<i>Bulk 2ML/s</i>	0.484	0.170	78	56	50	0.539	0.214
<i>SL-II 12</i>	0.960	1.379	36	22	50	0.625	0.159
<i>SL-II 6</i>	0.328	0.381	84	44	73	0.893	0.333

Table 1: Quantitative analysis of the PL spectra. Integrated intensity of the band gap emission peak (I_{GAP}), full width at half maximum of the band gap emission peak ($FWHM_{GAP}$), blue-shift of the band gap emission peak after RTA (Blue-shift $_{GAP}$) and integrated intensity of the sub-bandgap broad band (I_N) of samples *Bulk 1ML/s*, *Bulk 2ML/s*, *SL-II 12* and *SL-II 6*, either as-grown and after RTA.

Sample	J_{sc} (mA/cm 2)		V_{oc} (V)		Efficiency (%)		FF (%)	
	as-grown	RTA	as-grown	RTA	as-grown	RTA	as-grown	RTA
<i>Bulk 1ML/s</i>	26.62	17.95	0.39	0.51	6.07	5.73	65	63
<i>Bulk 2ML/s</i>	28.06	15.57	0.41	0.52	6.44	5.24	66	65
<i>SL-II 12</i>	6.16	2.50	0.38	0.50	1.02	0.70	46	56
<i>SL-II 6</i>	22.69	10.12	0.45	0.59	6.08	4.07	61	67

Table 2: Solar cell characteristic parameters of samples *Bulk 1ML/s*, *Bulk 2ML/s*, *SL-II 12* and *SL-II 6*, either as-grown and after RTA.